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Review Article

**A BRIEF OVERVIEW OF NEW TRENDS AND
ADVANCEMENTS IN THE ANALYSIS OF PESTICIDE
RESIDUES IN FRUITS****Tenali Vasantha¹, Devi Harathi¹, Kongitala Harshitha¹, Maliseti Bhavya Sree¹, Katepalli Chandana¹, Ramya Jonnalagadda^{1*}**Vijaya Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences for Women, Enikepadu, Vijayawada - 521108,
Andhra Pradesh, India.**Abstract:**

To ward off fruit-eating pests, the global use of pesticides has surged in recent years. Due to the high rate of direct consumption and even medical recommendations for fruits as nutritional supplements, consumers are understandably worried about pesticide residues. The health effects of pesticides and their metabolites can include cancer, respiratory issues, genotoxicity, neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption, and more. Therefore, it is crucial to appropriately regulate the use of pesticides in fields and examine the potential health risks associated with chemical residues. This concern has led to a reevaluation of the food safety situation and more educated legislative decisions on the random monitoring of pesticide residues in fruits. In most cases, a straightforward and fast analytical approach is necessary to determine the level of pesticide residues in fruits. Using various analytical techniques (like Gas Chromatography, Liquid Chromatography, and Biosensors) becomes critical, and regulatory directives are formed to regulate their amounts via the Maximum Residue Limit (MRL). In order to efficiently extract, identify, confirm, and quantify xenobiotics, a number of analytical approaches and procedures have been developed during the past years. This chapter gives an overview of the advanced detection methods like Hyperspectral imaging sensors, Electrochemical sensors, SERS based pesticide detection developed for pesticide residue analysis.

Keywords: Pesticide analysis, Hyperspectral imaging sensors, Electrochemical sensors, SERS-based pesticide detection

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INTRODUCTION:

The rapid urbanization and global population expansion in the last decade have led to a discernible rise in the use of pesticides. The health of people may be at risk if these residues which could include metabolites, breakdown products, or active pesticide ingredients are found in food. As a result, it's critical to inform customers about the possible risks associated with pesticide use [1]. Pesticides are usually discharged into the environment when humans consume contaminated food or water, and living in or near residential areas increases the risk of significant exposure. Even though this was a drop from the previous year, a sizable portion of India's food exports to the US and the EU—particularly fruits—were rejected in 2019 due to contamination [2].

Generally, an easy and quick logical process is demanded to determine the quantum of fungicide remainders in fruits. Chancing fungicide remainders using a variety of logical styles, including Gas chromatography (GC), Liquid Chromatography (LC), and biosensors, is thus essential. In the last two decades, multitudinous birth styles, varying in complexity, have been cooked to effectively prize, identify, validate, and measure xenobiotics which are time-consuming. This is followed by the establishment of a Maximum Residue Limit (MRL) by legislative action. Hence exploration is concentrated on more advanced ways with no or lower sample medication.

International institutions such as the Codex Alimentarius Commission (Codex) and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) are particularly concerned about harmonizing pesticide rules and restrictions since they support global trade. To make sure that MRLs are adhered to and that consumers are not exposed to pesticide concentrations that could be harmful to their health, the food supply is routinely checked [3].

HISTORY

Mercury and arsenic were the first "para-pesticides," utilized in the 1500s. These substances served as essential tools for growing popular crops until the 1940s, when man-made pesticides were created [4].

Before the invention of synthetic pesticides, the only options to gradually and laboriously control the continued invasion of pests were through simple procedures and natural materials. These days, management measures have taken the place of pest control methods. Chemical sterilizing agents and companion planting are two of the many strategies used in chemical pest management. The most common form of chemical pest control is the use of pesticides, which are chemical or biological treatments intended to kill, repel, or incapacitate a pest. It was standard practice to blend plants with straightforward materials or chemicals in the early days of pesticides. The anti-pest oil Amurea was discovered by the ancient Romans through crushing olive pits. As a result, novel and inventive pesticide compounds were found and employed as Elemental compounds that have been used for pest management since the dawn of agriculture, and in some cases, this method is still in use today. Elemental sulfur is said to have been among the first known chemical insecticides. The most widely used synthetic pesticide categories include carbamate, synthetic pyrethroids, nicotinoid, organochlorine (OCs), cyclodiene, organophosphate (OPs), and triazole because they stimulate crop development [5].

3. CLASSIFICATION

Among the many varieties of pesticides used to kill and deter pests are insecticides, fungicides, herbicides, garden chemicals, household disinfectants, and rodenticides [6].

The pesticide's chemical composition, its method of action the species it kills, and its entrance mechanism are the first three things to consider [7].

Based on where they come from, chemical pesticides are divided into four categories: pyrethroid, carbamate, organophosphate, and organochlorine. Biopesticides are a distinct category of pesticides that consist of compounds that are either naturally occurring or generated from living organisms, including plants, bacteria, and fungi.

The three main categories of biopesticides are plant-incorporated protectants, microbial pesticides, and biochemical pesticides.

Figure 1. Classification of pesticides

4. DISADVANTAGES OF PESTICIDE USAGE

In addition to short-term issues like headache, dizziness, and inflamed eyes and skin, they can cause long-term issues like cancer, thyroid, asthma, and diabetes. The type of pesticide, the degree of exposure, and the environmental conditions of the affected area are only a few of the numerous variables to take into account when estimating the risk associated with these pesticides [8].

They may also be harmful to those who apply pesticides at work or at home, eat or drink anything that has pesticide residue on it, or breathe in or come into touch with air that has been contaminated by pesticides. Children's physiology, temperament, and physical attributes make them more susceptible to pesticides than adults. 85% of all pesticides manufactured worldwide are used in agriculture to chemically manage a range of pests. Additionally, pesticides are used in public health campaigns to control vector-borne diseases like dengue and malaria as well as unwanted vegetation like grass and weeds [9].

5. FRUITS WITH LEADING EXISTENCE OF PESTICIDES

A list of the twelve fruits with the greatest concentrations of pesticides is published annually by the non-profit organization Environmental Working Group (EWG). Fruits with high pesticide concentrations include pears, apples, grapes, peaches, and cherries [10].

The Pesticide Data Program (USFDA) was recently introduced by the US Department of Agriculture. The maximum number of pesticides present in different

fruits and vegetables is displayed in Table 1 below [11].

Table 1: The greatest level of pesticides found in various fruits

S. No.	Fruit	Number of Pesticide Residues
1	Strawberries	45
2	Apples	47
3	Grapes	56
4	Cherries	42
5	Tomatoes	35

6. DETECTION TECHNIQUES

To identify the pesticide and its concentration, modern methods use sensors, automation, Artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning (ML) algorithms. However, the module requires a lot of training in diverse situations. The advanced detection techniques discussed in the chapter include hyperspectral imaging sensor, electrochemical sensor, SERS detection

6.1. Hyperspectral imaging sensor

The principle of spectroscopy, which captures several images of a specific region at varying wavelengths, is the basis of hyperspectral imaging. By using the electromagnetic spectrum, it can produce a spectrum that is color-coded as RGB. A time-sequential bands scanner (spectral scanner) takes pictures of a scene using a variety of wavelengths, and this camera can read those photos. The photograph was taken by the EMCCD camera. The hyperspectral spectrograph processes it, polarizes it, and finally displays it on the screen using the RGB light spectrum. Spectra within the 865.11 – 1711.71 nm range can be acquired by the detector.

Figure 2. Hyperspectral imaging sensor

The high spectral resolution of hyperspectral imaging makes it useful for tasks like feature discrimination and object identification. The device's intricacy and high price tag are its main drawbacks. Since each material has its distinct properties, hyperspectral imaging is used to learn about them. For glyphosate and butachlor detection, near-infrared hyperspectral imaging is employed. Detection of wavelengths is the foundation of infrared hyperspectral imaging. A sequential projections approach is employed to identify the effective wavelengths, and pesticide categorization is accomplished by linear discriminant analysis.

6.2. Electrochemical sensor

The most prevalent and harmful chemical to humans, methyl parathion, can be detected with an electrochemical sensor. An item can detect a shift in resistance, voltage, or current when submerged in a conductivity liquid. Organic fruits free of pesticides have readings between 500 and 550 ppm, whereas

when fruits sample with pesticides has been immersed in the electrically conducting liquid the levels typically fall between 600 and 850 ppm. Though they are less expensive and offer superior precision and repeatability, electrochemical sensors do have some drawbacks, such as a short operating time and a narrow temperature resistance range.

6.3. SERS detection

SERS, or surface-enhanced Raman scattering, is a low-cost and rapid alternative to traditional laboratory procedures for detecting pesticide residue. The Raman effect is based on the vibrating of electrons, which can be observed as a change in energy state when excited. Light with high intensity and a small region is used to evaluate samples because it causes them to gain energy. The Raman effect occurs when there is a difference between the incident and reflected photon wavelengths, even when some light is reflected. A nano SERS chip array using a Raman sensor based on a smartphone was created.

Figure 3. SERS detection

The SERS chip is attached to a portable scanning electron microscope (SEM) by a port, and the sample is then inserted into a slit for scanning. The SEM is linked to a cloud database. Pressing the start button initiates the detection process, which involves pointing the associated accessory at the fruit to identify the pesticide. The data set is initially captured without any pesticide, and then it is supplemented with a variety of pesticides and mixture modifications. When the gadget scans a sample, the AI instantly retrieves the data from the cloud database and presents the graph. To compare the unknown pesticide, it is necessary to collect sample data. SERS technology is fast, requires no sample preparation, and may be applied to gases, solids, and liquids. The lack of sensitivity and inapplicability to metals and alloys are the key disadvantages. Additionally, SERS can quickly identify pesticide residue on a variety of materials [12].

7. CONCLUSION:

Pesticides, even in trace amounts, can hurt consumers' health. Consequently, it is essential to keep an eye on pesticide residues in food products. Because of matrix interference effects and the limited sensitivity of various detection systems, it could be challenging to identify all pesticides directly. Owing to the difficulties in identifying pesticides new approaches were developed in addition to improving current methods to increase the accuracy of analytical data. Policies and restrictions can differ between nations. It might be challenging for food laboratories to select techniques and tools for measuring pesticide residues to stay up to date with the most recent limitations because the list of target compounds and matrices is changed regularly. Due to the rapid and accurate outcomes that may be predicted with the use of AI,

ML, and automation, their potential applications in the future are vast. For both practical and scientific reasons, it would be wise to use cutting-edge technology to identify pesticide residues.

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